

Serruria florida Blushing bride

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Group: Eudicot

Size: 0.6 – 1.5 meters in height

Distribution:

The blushing bride occurs close to Franschhoek on mountain slopes in soils derived from granite. It is Critically Endangered as it is threatened by alien invasive species such as hakea and pines. Too frequent fires are a critical threat to the remaining wild populations, as immature plants are not given enough time to produce seeds that will rejuvenate the underground seed bank.

Importance:

The blushing bride is one of the most delicate members of the Proteaceae family. *Serruria* has grown into an important member of the indigenous floriculture industry of South Africa. On the one hand the conservation of this endangered member is critical, but on the other the delicate flowers are creating jobs and earning international value on export of flowers.

PromethION Sequencing Report:

Output: 34.3 Gigabases

Approximate N50: 13.76 kilobases

Draft Genome Assembly Statistics:

Assembler used: Flye

Genome Length: 0.51 Gigabases

BUSCO completeness score: 96.7% [Single: 87.5%, Duplicated: 9.2%]

BUSCO database: viridiplantae

Assembly N50: 244.21 kilobases

Contig number: 7 224

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